

Environmental and Economics impacts of the emission reduction in the Steel industry sector in Brazil

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Steel industry is responsible for 7% of global GHG emissions

- Hard-to-abate sector
- Paris Agreement

Source: IEA, 2020. Iron and Steel Technology Roadmap - Towards more sustainable steelmaking

Technology	tCO ₂ /t steel	CAPEX (Euro/tonne)	TRL Status
BF-BOF	1.1 - 2.2	386-442	9
EAF	0.4 - 1.1	184	9
BF-BOF CCS	0.9	411-471	5-8
Smelting Reduction	1.2 - 2.3	393	9
Smelting Reduction (CCS)	0.0 - 0.2	418-478	7
DRI-EAF	0.63 - 1.15	414	9
H-DRI EAF	0 - 0.025	550-900	5-7
EW	0.20 - 0.29	639	4-5

E+ Energy Transition Institute (2022). Scoping Paper on the Brazilian Steel Industry Decarbonization. Rio de Janeiro/RJ. Brazil

2. The gap

- Many studies analyzed the decarbonization pathways of the steel industry
- Understand the impacts on other sectors regarding the emissions and the economy
- *”Additional knowledge is needed to understand sectoral interactions in the transformation processes” (IPCC,2022)*

¹IPCC, 2022: Industry - Climate Change 2022: Mitigation of Climate Change. Contribution of Working Group III to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change

What are the environmental and economical impacts of the decarbonization of the Brazilian steel industry?

- What are the changes in the emission profile in other economic sectors?
- What is the change in the GDP?
- What is the change in the level of employment?

4. Methodology

4. Scenarios

Scenario 1

Decreasing emissions aligned to net-zero pathways

Only well known Technologies:

- **DR-NG (0 → 24%)**
- EAF (24 → 37%)
- BF-BOF Charcoal (7 → 36%)
- BF-BOF Coal (69 → 7%)

Scenario 2

Efforts to achieve higher emission reduction

Hydrogen playing a key role

- **DR-H2 (0 → 24%)**
- EAF (24 → 37%)
- BF-BOF Charcoal (7 → 36%)
- BF-BOF Coal (69 → 7%)

Hebeda, Otto, et al. "Pathways for deep decarbonization of the Brazilian iron and steel industry." *Journal of Cleaner Production* 401 (2023): 136675.

5. Results – Steel industry results

5. Results – Scenario 1

99% of the reduction happens in the BF-BOF activity

5. Results – Scenario 2

99% of the reduction happens in the BF-BOF activity

5. Results – Economic

GDP variation

Scenario 1	0.28%
Scenario 2	0.32%

Conclusion

- Emission reduction in the steel sector
- With a little increase in other sectors

- Creation of jobs and increase the economic activity

- Infrastructure barriers
- Technology development
- Policy instruments

Next steps

- Demand side measures scenarios with the change of production
- Investment required to this energy transition
- Future demand scenarios
- Changes in the steel production in other countries